

Translational Properties, Velocity Field and Fisher Information in Quantum Mechanics

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A process exists in the literature (1) of creating an information term based on Fisher's information using spatial density P and adding it to a classical Lagrangian based on a velocity field i.e. $\text{velocity} = dS/dx$. Maximization of S and P is performed and a differential equation in terms of spatial density and S is obtained. Finally, it is noted that a change of variables: $W = \sqrt{p} \exp(iS/\hbar)$ may simplify the differential equation so that it becomes the Schrodinger equation with W as the wavefunction. In this note, we consider the wavefunction as appearing "naturally" as a normalization constant when using conditional probability and argue that W is the velocity field. Given that the Schrodinger equation includes a term of the form $-1/2m d/dx d/dx W$ (in 1-D) i.e. the first derivative is related to the average velocity and the second to the ensemble average of p^*p . This follows because unnormalized conditional probability $f(p,x)$ is the Fourier basis function i.e. $\exp(ipx)$.

The second derivative term $-1/2m d/dx d/dx W$ may be obtained from a Lagrangian containing $(d/dx W) (d/dx W)$, thus formally one may use maximization to obtain the Schrodinger equation at a level using W directly. The maximization form, however, is identical to the "classical translational" form (2) of Fisher's information. Thus, it seems that the Fourier basis $\exp(ipx)$ and the maximization of classical translational Fisher's information are linked. In this note, we wish to investigate this in further detail.

We also use translational properties together with conditional probability to show that $f(p,x)$ where $P(p/x) = a(p) f(p/x) / [\text{Sum over } p a(p) f(p/x)]$ is $\exp(ipx)$. In particular, we obtain an equation taken from the translation of the conservation of energy equation at point x to $x + \Delta x$. This links $df(p,x)/dx$ with $-dV/dx$ (the force). If the force is stochastic and yields "k" momentum hits, $-dV/dx = \text{Sum over } k kV_k(x)$. We argue that $df(p,x)/dx$ also brings out this k term i.e. is an eigenfunction of k i.e. $-idf(p,x)/dx = k f(p,x)$ yields $\exp(ipx)$ as a solution. This $f(p,x)$ is automatically an orthonormal basis (multiplied by an appropriate constant) and helps to show why the "momentum operator" is linked to a "translation operator" i.e. d/dx .

The bound state Schrodinger equation is considered in this note.

Fisher Information Approach of (1)

There are two points we wish to highlight regarding the derivation of the Schrodinger equation in (1). First, only the concept of spatial density is needed. The wavefunction is introduced only as a change of variable to simplify the form of a differential equation. Secondly, the derivation is based partly on a classical velocity field S and partly on a Fisher (classical translational) information term defined by:

$$1/(P^*P) dP/dx_i dP/dx_j \text{ where } P(x) = \text{spatial density}$$

The classical Lagrangian is defined as:

$$\int dt dx^n P(x) \{dS/dt (\text{partial}) + .5 g_{ij} dS/dx_i dS/dx_j\}$$

To this is added the Fisher information for translation:

$$\int dt dx^n P(x) .5b g_{ij} 1/(P^*P) dP/dx_i dP/dx_j \quad \text{where } b \text{ is a Lagrange multiplier.}$$

The variation (with respect to S and P) leads to a differential equation in S and P. Finally, the transformation:

$$W(x)=\text{wavefunction} = \text{sqrt}(P) \exp(iS/\hbar) \text{ is used to obtain the Schrodinger equation.}$$

Conditional Probability

If one considers a stochastic system such that a particle has a certain probability $P(p/x)$ to have momentum p at x and is subject to a stochastic potential which on average (in time) is $V(x)$, it seems one has an ensemble scenario (with all time values removed). Thus, if one insists that classical averages exist at each x point, one has:

$$[\text{Sum over } p \ p^*p/2m \ a(p) \ f(p,x)] / [\text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \ f(p,x)] + V(x) = E \quad ((1))$$

where $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \ f(p,x)$, the wavefunction, appears immediately, but spatial density does not appear at all. (To obtain spatial density, one may argue that within a δx , a particle receives a stochastic hit from the potential $V(x)$, changing it from p_1 to p_2 . Thus, if there is only one hit in δx , there are pairs $a(p_1)f(p_1,x)a(p_2)f(p_2,x)$ for all possible combinations and we argue this yields spatial density.

So far, $W(x)$ is not linked to a velocity field, i.e. there is no indication that $-id/dx W(x) / W(x)$ is the ensemble average of momentum. In previous notes, we tried to argue that $W(x)$ is related to $V(x)$ and $-dV/dx$ yields momentum hits. Thus, we argued that ultimately $-id/dx W(x)/W(x)$ does yield the ensemble average of velocity, but only because of its link to the behaviour of force. Here, we wish to consider an alternative argument based on translating from x to $x + \delta x$. Consider ((1)) written as:

$$[\text{Sum over } p \ p^*p/2m \ f(p,x) \ a(p)] + V(x)W(x) = E W(x) \quad ((2))$$

Next, consider a point $x+\delta x$ and the first order change:

$$[\text{Sum over } p \ p^*p/2m \ d/dx \ f(p,x) \ a(p)] + dV(x)/dx W + V dW/dx = E dW/dx \quad ((3))$$

In a previous note (3), we argued that $f(p,x)$ is a basis function. We use this result, but at this point it is not clear what basis function to use. If $V(x)$ is random and gives "k" momentum hits with a probability $V_k(x)$, one may argue that $V_k(kx)$ where $V(x)= \text{Sum over } k \ V_k(kx)$. If one wishes ((3)) to hold for the coefficient of each basis function, then a possible solution is to have:

$$f(p,x) V_k(kx) = f(p+k,x) \quad ((4))$$

Furthermore, if $dV(kx)/dx = k$ function, one would wish to have this property apply to $f(p+k, x)$, so it too should be of the form: $f(p+k, x)$. Using these two properties gives a solution of:

$$f(p, x) = \exp(ipx) \quad (5)$$

Alternatively, one may argue that $d/dx f(p, x) = k f(p, x)$ is sufficient. This yields an eigenfunction problem with $\exp(ipx)$ as a solution. This is automatically an orthonormal basis (with a normalization constant.) Thus, translational considerations together with Force = $-dV/dx$ imparting "k" hits of momentum seem to be sufficient for choosing $f(p, x) = \exp(ipx)$. This helps to show why the momentum operator (acting on the ensemble W) is related to the translation operator.

Thus, the Fourier basis yields a solution to the problem. At this point, one may stop, but it is interesting to note that $W(x)$ becomes a velocity and kinetic energy field because:

$$\langle p \rangle = -i \frac{d}{dx} \ln(W) \quad \text{and} \quad \langle p^2 \rangle / 2m = - \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W / W \quad (6)$$

Here $\langle \rangle$ represents an ensemble average using conditional probability $P(p/x)$. We wish to point out that ((6)) is a property of the Fourier basis function $\exp(ipx)$. This, however, means that one may maximize the term:

Integral $dx \frac{d}{dx} W \frac{d}{dx} W$ with respect to W to obtain $-d/dx d/dx W$.

As a result, the problem could have been formulated as a maximization problem in the first place without any knowledge of the basis function $\exp(ipx)$. There would, however, have to be a reason to maximize $(dW/dx)(dW/dx)$. We argue that $(dW/dx)(dW/dx)$ is of the form of the "classical translational" Fisher information (1) ie.

$$P \left(\frac{d \ln(P)}{dx} \right) \left(\frac{d \ln(P)}{dx} \right) = 4 \left(\frac{dW}{dx} \right) \left(\frac{dW}{dx} \right) \quad \text{with } P=W^*W$$

. Thus, there seems to be a statistical argument related to the choice of the Fourier basis, and we wish to point this out.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that applying translational ideas to the conservation of energy equation at point x (using conditional probability $P(p/x) = a(p)f(p, x)/W$ which contains $W(x)$ the wavefunction), it is possible to show that $-idf(p, x)/dx = p f(p, x)$ which yields $f(p, x) = \exp(ipx)$ as a solution. This is an orthogonal basis. The result follows from the idea that $V(x+\delta x)$ leads to dV/dx which is related to force which is related to dp/dt . Thus, if the force is stochastic, it should give different momentum k hits. Thus: $-dV/dx = \text{Sum over } k \quad k V_k(kx)$ and we find that $df(p, x)/dx$ must behave in a similar manner if the conservation of energy equation at x is to also hold at

$x + \delta x$. Thus, this may help to explain why the momentum operator in quantum mechanics, which acts on an ensemble i.e. the wavefunction, is related to a translational operator i.e. d/dx .

As a result of having $f(p,x)=\exp(ipx)$, W becomes a velocity and kinetic energy field. Thus, at x one has: $-\frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W / W (1/2m) + V(x)W(x) = E W(x)$. The first term on the LHS may follow from maximizing: $\int (d \ln W / dx) (d \ln W / dx)$ with respect to W , but this term is equivalent to maximizing Fisher's information for classical translation motion (2). Thus, we argue that the maximization of classical translational Fisher's information seems to be linked to the basis function $\exp(ipx)$ which in turn is linked to translational motion and the idea of force $=-dV/dx$ yielding "k" momentum hits.

References

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